

THE CHAIN TERMINATING STEP IN THE CATALYSED VINYL POLYMERIZATION

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A suggestion that the chain termination by catalyst fragments is a very important factor in deciding the molecular weights, overall rates etc., is made. An extreme case when only such termination occurs in a polymerization reaction is analysed theoretically and the size distribution function deduced. The consistency of such a hypothesis with previously observed data is shown.

In the common vinyl polymerizations, catalysed by peroxide type of catalysts, the generally accepted view is that the chain termination occurs by the mutual combination of two growing radicals, which for brevity we shall call combination termination process, as shown below.

where an asterisk indicates a free radical and M stands for a monomer unit. The main arguments are (cf. Herrington, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1942, **40**, 236) :

(1) The existence of a maxima in the size distribution curve of the polymer (Schulz, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1939, **43B**, 25, 49).

(2) The slope of the overall velocity curve is proportional to the square root of the catalyst concentration.

The bulk of the available data supports such a view, and the mechanism may be substantially correct.

In a previous communication (*communicated*) we demonstrated the enormous activity of potassium persulphate in solution polymerization of styrene in diethylene glycol. Our findings were that this catalyst was about 100 times more active than benzoyl peroxide in the same solvent and that the molecular weight of the product in the first instance was more than five to six times than in the latter case. These two facts appear at first sight to be mutually incongruent as the general view is that the faster the initiation, the smaller the molecular weight, as described by the following equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Molecular weight (number average)} &= \frac{\text{Velocity of propagation}}{\text{Velocity of termination}} \\ &= \frac{\text{Velocity of propagation}}{\text{Velocity of initiation}} \end{aligned}$$

To meet this situation, a suggestion was made that the chain termination mechanism was not the same in the two cases. We assumed that in the case of peroxide-catalysed polymerizations there was a possibility that the termination might occur by the mutual collision of a free radical produced by the catalyst and the growing polymer chain (which we shall concisely term "the radical termination" process) as described by the equation,

and that this mechanism did not play a very substantial part in the case of the persulphate.

The present communication is intended to analyse the effect of such a termination process on the overall rate and on the size distribution curve of the polymers formed.

The Kinetic Frame

We are neglecting the chain transfer etc. which do not have any direct influence in our case.

In the above, we have supposed that the catalyst radical is deactivated in only two ways. This is, however, not the actual case and various side reactions occur by which the catalyst is decomposed. These side reactions, however, have no influence on the polymerization reactions except that they reduce the effective concentration of the catalyst. The common procedure is to introduce a "peroxide wastage factor" to make allowance for these side reactions (Nozaki and Bartlett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1686).

In all previous work, k_{t_1} was assumed to be equal to k_{t_2} , which no doubt simplifies the mathematics but tends to produce the impression that the "radical" termination process has no significant effect in the size distribution of the polymers formed. However, k_{t_1} cannot be equal to k_{t_2} , and this can at least be indicated in the case of solvents where the polymer is insoluble by following a simple argument as given below.

Evans and Baxendale (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, **43**, 215) have shown that for such a system the chain termination may be essentially that of coagulation of colloidal solutions, as given by Smoluchowski and by modifying Somoluchowski's equation for such processes, he derives the equation,

$$k_t = \frac{8RT}{3000 \eta} f(n)$$

$$\text{where } f(n) = \left[2 + \left(\frac{n_1}{n_2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} + \left(\frac{n_2}{n_1} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \right] / 4 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of monomer units in the radicals taking part in termination.

In the case of usual combination termination we have average n_2 virtually equal to n_1 and hence $f(n) \approx$ unity. However, in "radical" termination process this is far from the

case because for the production of polymers of molecular weight nearing 20,000, $n_1:n_2$ is about 200 and hence

$$f_2(n) = \frac{2 + \left(\frac{200}{1}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{1}{200}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{4} \approx 2$$

and therefore $\frac{k_{t_2}}{k_{t_1}}$ is of the order of two.

Here of course, we have made the rather questionable assumption that k_{t_2} can be calculated by equation (1), because the above equation has been deduced for the mutual coagulation of two colloidal particles, whereas in our calculation only one of the two fragments is insoluble and hence the equation is not strictly valid.

The possibility that the benzoate radical may also terminate (in addition to initiation) is very plausible. The recent observations of Mayo and Gregg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1284) indicate that any free radical can behave both as a catalyst and as an inhibitor and generally both concurrently depending upon conditions and in fact, the phenomenon of inhibition, which is only a limiting case of our radical termination, is shown by the above authors to run concurrently with initiation in the case of the triphenylmethyl radical and leads them to the conclusion that "the differences between them (initiation and inhibition) are quantitative rather than qualitative".

The Overall Rate

The consideration of only the combination termination process leads to the familiar equation (Evans, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, Disc. **2**, 271)

$$-\frac{dM}{dt} = k_p \sqrt{\frac{k_1 c}{k_t}} [M] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where M is the concentration of the monomer and k_1 , the rate of decomposition of the catalyst concentrations. Redington (*J. Poly. Sci.*, 1948, **3**, 503) introduces a correction $(1-w)$ to the catalyst concentration (w being the "peroxide wastage" factor) to explain his experimental results, and uses the modified equation,

$$-\frac{dM}{dt} = k_p \sqrt{\frac{(1-w)k_1}{k_{t_1}}} c [M] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

We now consider the extreme case that the termination occurs exclusively by the 'radical' termination process. In this case assuming the usual steady state equations we proceed as follows: We have,

$$\frac{d[R]}{dt} = k_1 c - k_t [R][M] - k_{t_2} [R][M] = 0$$

$$\text{and } \frac{d[M^*]}{dt} = k_1 [R][M] - k_2 [R][M^*] = 0$$

These two when solved gives,

$$[M^*] = \frac{k_1 [M]}{k_2} \text{ and } R = \frac{k_1 c}{2k_1 [M]}$$

And hence, the overall rate

$$\begin{aligned} - \frac{d[M]}{dt} &= k_p [M^*][M] + k_t [R][M] \\ &= k_p \frac{k_1}{k_2} [M]^2 + \frac{1}{2} k_1 c \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

[R and M* being the catalyst fragment and the growing chains respectively].

The equation is true only if $c \neq 0$. This equation differs from the standard equation (equation 2) in the important respect that the rate is here linear with respect to the square of the monomer concentration instead of being proportional to its first power.

Schulz and his co-workers, (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1942, **51B**, 75; 1938, **39B**, 246) and Mark and Josefowitz (cf. Matheson, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 584) have shown the polymerization of methyl methacrylate, styrene, vinyl acetate and isoprene catalysed by benzoyl peroxide, or of styrene catalysed by tetraphenyl succinonitrite do not follow the simple equation (2) and can be expressed better by equation (5)

$$- \frac{d[M]}{dt} = \text{Const.} \times c^{\frac{1}{2}} [M] \left[\frac{k [M]}{1 + k [M]} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \quad (5)$$

where k is a constant.

To obtain this equation theoretically Schulz assumes that the monomer and the catalyst exist as an equilibrium-complex (k being the equilibrium constant) and that this complex rearranges unimolecularly to give the first radical unit of the growing chain

Similar views were expressed by Cuthbertson, Gee and Rideal (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1939, **A**, 170, 300) to explain their results on the vinyl acetate polymerization. Matheson (*loc. cit.*) suggests an alternative explanation based on the rapidly reversible dissociation of the peroxide molecules within a cage of solvent molecules. However, it is interesting to note that the equation (5) which has a power > 1 in M stands midway between equation (2) with power unity on M and equation (4) deduced by us with an exponent of 2 on M. Thus, a plausible explanation of the observed fact may be found in the simultaneous occurrence of the two termination process in actual reaction.

The results of Redington (*J. Poly. Sci.*, 1948, 3, 503) reveal certain interesting features. He finds that lauryl, *p*-dichlorobenzoyl and 2-4 dichlorobenzoyl peroxide, though have greater rates of decomposition than benzoyl peroxide, initiate the polymerization to a much smaller extent, the results being that the overall yields of the polymers are smaller. This he explains successfully by introducing '*w*', the peroxide wastage factor as mentioned previously. The effect of *w* is to decrease the effective concentration of the catalyst *i.e.*, to decrease the effective value of k_1 in equation (2). It is doubtful, however, if this simple explanation of Redington explains the whole picture because it can be easily shown that the ratio of the molecular weight averages of the polymers formed by the two catalysts may be given by

$$\frac{\bar{v}_1}{\bar{v}_2} = \sqrt{\frac{(1-w) [k_1]_2}{(1-w) [k_1]_1}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Hence we might expect, the higher the $(1-w) k_1$ value, the lower would be the molecular weight. However, exactly opposite occurs in the case of *p*-chlorobenzoyl peroxide, as shown in Table I, calculated from the data of Redington. (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I

Temp.	Catalyst.	k_1 (hr ⁻²)	<i>w</i> .	$(1-w)k_1$.	Sp. viscosity.
100°	Benzoyl peroxide	1.65	0.08	1.52	1.94
	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoyl peroxide	1.5	0.12	1.32	1.74
74.8°	Benzoyl peroxide	0.066	0.15	0.056	2.87
	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoyl peroxide	0.80	0.52	0.042	3.62
61.0°	Benzoyl peroxide	0.0083	0.23	0.0071	4.35
	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoyl peroxide	0.012	0.54	0.0055	3.81
49.9°	Benzoyl peroxide	0.0019	0.29	0.0013	5.08
	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoyl peroxide	0.003	0.72	0.0008	4.81
34.8°	Benzoyl peroxide	0.00014	0.39	0.00057	6.40
	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoyl peroxide	0.00030	0.81	0.000057	5.48

*In this case the values of μ_p are as expected.

This peculiar behaviour of *p*-chlorobenzoyl peroxide may be explained by observing that *w* is always greater in this case than that of benzoyl peroxide. *w* is all the peroxide molecules which do not initiate a polymerization chain and hence must include also the amount used in radical termination process, and this process is more prominent in the former case

than in the latter, and we shall show below that this process tends to make the molecular weight lower.

Some similar observations have also been published by Cooper (*Nature*, 1948, **162**, 897, 927) in two very recent notes.

The Size Distribution Function

In the case of termination by combination, Herrington and Robertson give for the size distribution function,

$$\frac{d[M_r]}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{A^2 \theta^2}{[M]^2} (r-2) e^{-\sqrt{\frac{A \theta}{[M]}} (r-2)} \dots \dots \dots \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } \theta = \sqrt{\frac{k_t}{k_p}}$$

and M_r the concentration of the polymer with chain length r . A is the rate of initiation of the growing chain i.e., $A = k_1 c = \sum_1^{\infty} k_t [M_r^*]^2$

Equation (7) reduces to

$$\frac{d[M_r]}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{k_1^2 c^2}{[M]^2} \theta^2 (r-2) e^{-\frac{(r-2) k_t^{\frac{1}{2}} c^{\frac{1}{2}} \theta}{M}} \dots \dots \dots \quad (8)$$

This equation is peculiar in the respect that there is a maxima in the $\frac{d[M_r]}{dt}$ versus r curve.

As we have mentioned in the beginning that this is the strongest argument in favour of a combination termination in actual polymerization process, as Schulz (*loc. cit.*) pointed out, and his experimental curves have a very close resemblance to equation (8). However, Herrington (*loc. cit.*) points out that a maximum in the size distribution curve may arise from other mechanisms, but all these could at once be eliminated by kinetic considerations.

For the case of termination exclusively by catalyst radical, the molecular distribution can be easily arrived at by a process essentially that of Herrington and Robertson, as shown below. We have,

$$\frac{d[M^*]}{dt} = k_p [M^*_{r-1}][M] - k_p [M^*_r][M] - k_{t_2} [M^*_r][R] = 0$$

And if we write A for the initiation rates of the radical chains

$$A = k_p [M^*][M] + k_{t_2} [M_1^*][R]$$

... ..

$$k_p [M^*_{r-1}][M] = k_p [M^*_r][M] + k_{t_2} [M^*_r][R]$$

Summing to infinity

$$A = k_{t_2} [R] \sum_1^{\infty} [M_r]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} k_1 c.$$

Rearranging the above set of equations we get

$$\begin{aligned} A &= k_1 [M_1^*] [M] \left[1 + \frac{k_{t_2} [R]}{k_p [M]} \right] \\ &= k_p [M_1^*] [M] \left[1 + \frac{k_{t_2} k_1 c}{2 k_p k_1 [M]^2} \right] \quad (\text{by substituting the values of } [R]) \\ &= k_p [M_1^*] [M] \left[1 + \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

where $\beta = \frac{k_{t_2} k_1}{2 k_p k_1}$

The rth equation of this set being

$$k_p [M_{r-1}^*] [M] = k_p [M_r^*] [M] \left[1 + \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2} \right]$$

Multiplying both sides up to rth equation we get,

$$A = k_p [M_r^*] [M] \left[1 + \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2} \right]^r$$

Taking logs and using the approximation

$$\log(1+x) = x \text{ for large values of } x,$$

We get

$$\log A = \log k_p [M_r^*] [M] + r \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2}$$

and thus,

$$\begin{aligned} k_p [M_r^*] [M] &= A e^{-r \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} k_1 c e^{-r \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2}} \end{aligned}$$

Or

$$[M_r^*] = \frac{k_1 c}{2 k_p [M]} e^{-r \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

This is our radical distribution equation.

Now, we have,

$$\frac{d[M_r]}{dt} = k_{t_2} [M_r^*] [R] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

Substituting the value of $[M_r^*]$ from the radical distribution equation we have,

$$\frac{d[M_r]}{dt} = \frac{k_{t_2} k_1^2 c^2}{2 k_p k_1 [M]^2} e^{-r \frac{\beta c}{[M]^2}}$$

Writing α for $\frac{k_{t_2} k_1^2}{2 k_p k_1}$ we get our required size distribution curve

$$\frac{dM_r}{dt} = \frac{\alpha c^2}{[M]^2} e^{-r \frac{\beta_0}{[M]}} \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

The size distribution equation (11) is clearly an exponentially decreasing curve with no maximum. The effect of radical termination occurring concurrently with the usual termination by combination would therefore be to shift the maxima towards lower chain length which might be one of the factors responsible for the unexpected lower molecular weight in Redington's results.

C O N C L U S I O N

The hypothesis that the peroxide radicals can readily terminate a growing chain brings us face to face with the problem of determination of the factors which make a free radical very effective in such processes. This question naturally is bound with the stability of the free radicals and their average life on which very little is known. Some considerations similar to the alternating effect (Walling and Mayo, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1948, 3, 895) in copolymerization may also have some bearing on the problem. As more information on various catalysts is becoming increasingly available, it seems that a complete overlooking of this role of the catalyst radical has been too drastic an oversimplification in many cases.

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